

The rice crop received 861.9 mm total rainfall in 1985-86 and 1,050.1 mm in 1987-88; lentil received 51.8 mm in 1985-86 and 74.1 mm in 1987-88.

Application of butachlor in wet season and prometryn in dry season, with and without paraquat, reduced weed dry weight in rice the most (Table 1). In lentil, interculture with intrarow hand weeding reduced weed dry weight the most.

Highest rice grain and straw yields were with interculture twice plus intrarow hand weeding, followed by hand weeding and chemical control. Highest lentil yield was with preemergence application of butachlor in wet season and prometryn in dry season. Interculture was least effective in both crops.

Table 2. Economics^a of weed control treatments in rice - lentil sequence at BHU, Varanasi, India, 1985-88.

Treatment	Mean yield (t/ha)				Value of produce (\$/ha)	Total cost of land preparation and weed control (\$/ha)	Return to land preparation and weed control (\$/ha)	Benefit to-cost ratio
	Rice		Lentil					
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw				
T1	0.4	3.0	0.8	1.3	406.35	250.00	156.35	0.63
T2	2.6	4.4	1.2	1.7	831.07	367.65	463.42	1.26
T3	1.3	3.7	0.9	1.3	551.72	279.41	272.31	0.97
T4	3.2	4.8	1.2	1.4	927.93	308.82	619.11	2.01
T5	2.9	4.1	0.8	1.1	749.00	280.88	468.12	1.67
T6	3.0	4.2	1.3	1.6	926.41	295.66	630.75	2.13
T7	2.9	4.2	1.3	2.3	940.29	306.29	634.00	2.07

^aPrice of produce: Rice: grain - \$132.35/t, straw - \$14.71/t; lentil: grain - 330.88/t, straw - 21.74/t. Cost of treatments: Land Preparation (1) \$8.82/ha, hand weeding (1) \$29.41/ha, interculture by dryland weeder (1) \$7.35/ha, intrarow hand weeding (1) \$7.35/ha, spraying of herbicide (1) \$4.41/ha, butachlor at \$13.23/kg ai, prometryn at \$13.78/kg ai, and paraquat at \$23.85/kg ai. General cost of cultivation: \$214.72/ha.

On a pooled mean basis, highest net return was with preemergence application of butachlor in rice and prometryn following paraquat in lentil (Table 2). □

Managing other pests

Effect of bund dimensions on rodent infestation in irrigated ricefields

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We surveyed 83 transplanted irrigated ricefields 1987-88 to examine the relationship between rodent infestation and the width and height of bunds. Rodent infestation was measured as the

Correlation between rodent infestation and bund dimensions.^a Hyderabad, India.

Bund variable	Crop stage ^b (<i>r</i> value)				
	Seedling (13)	Tillering (19)	Booting (17)	Flowering (21)	Maturity (13)
Width (W)	0.87**	0.79**	0.82**	0.44*	0.77**
Height (H)	0.83**	0.57	0.78**	0.78**	0.63**
W × H	0.80**	0.63**	0.78**	0.64**	0.61**

^aSignificance at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ^bNumbers in parentheses indicate sample size.

number of live burrows/ 10 m.

The correlation between rodent infestation and bund width was significant at all stages of the crop growth; that between infestation and

bund height was significant at all stages except tillering (see table) when rodents establish themselves. Bund volume (height × width) and infestation were directly related. □

Farming systems

Rice-based cropping sequences for rainfed conditions in midhills of Uttar Pradesh

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Spring rice (Mar-Sep) is the predominant upland crop in the midhills

of Uttar Pradesh. Because currently available spring rice varieties have long duration, cropping cereals and legumes in rotation is not feasible. The most popular 2-yr cropping sequence is upland rice (Mar-Sep) - wheat (Oct-May) - finger millet (Jun-Oct) - fallow (Nov-Mar), for a 150% cropping intensity.

After shortduration (110 d Jun-Oct) upland rice variety VL Dhan 163 was released, we evaluated 5 intensive cropping sequences for production and return 1985-86 at the Hawalbagh

experiment farm (1,250 m, 29 °36'N, 79° 40'). The split-plot design had crop sequence as the main plot and organic and inorganic fertilization as subplots, with four replications. Soil was a sandy loam with medium fertility.

Rainfed short-duration rice was direct seeded in the wet season, followed by wheat variety VL 421, barley VLB 1, pea VL Matar 1, lentil VL Masur 1, and rapeseed T9 in the dry season. Rice was sown the first week of Jun, the winter crops were planted the third week of Oct. Organic fertilizer treatment was